

Derivatives of Salicylic Acid. Part I. 3-Nitro- and 5-Nitro-salicylic Acids.

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In continuation of work done by Meldrum and Shah on sulphosalicylic acid (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 1986) it was intended to prepare the nitrosulphosalicylic acids. For this purpose it was necessary to obtain the 3-nitro- and 5-nitro-salicylic acids.

Work on the preparation of these acids, from salicylic acids, has been done by Griess (*Ber.*, 1878, 11, 1730), Hübner (*Annalen*, 1879, 198, 258), Deninger (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1890, (ii), 42, 550) and by Meldola, Foster, and Brightman (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 111, 536). The last named authors heated salicylic acid with dilute nitric acid on the water-bath for an hour: they isolated only 5-nitrosalicylic acid. Deninger used nitrous acid; he stated that at a high temperature 3-nitrosalicylic acid, and at a low temperature 5-nitrosalicylic acid is produced.

Following closely the methods of Meldola, Foster and Brightman and of Deninger, we obtained always a mixture of the 3- and 5-nitro acid. We found also that the separation of these acids with the help of their barium salts, recommended by Hübner, is slow and uncertain. We have, therefore, devised a simple method of nitration, and also a method of separating the two isomers that depends on the properties of the mono- and the di-potassium salts. The appearance and the solubilities of these salts are given in the following table:—

<i>Salt.</i>	<i>3-Nitro acid.</i>	<i>5-Nitro acid.</i>
$\text{HO}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\cdot\text{NO}_2\cdot\text{COOK}$.	Pale yellow wisps of needles; solubility 0.94 (81°).	Shining golden yellow needles; easily soluble in water: Solubility 6.60 (81°).
$\text{KO}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\cdot\text{NO}_2\cdot\text{COOK}$.	Crimson-red needles, soluble in potassium hydroxide solution.	Yellow needles, difficultly soluble in potassium hydroxide solution.

The 3-nitro acid can be separated as monopotassium salt, and the 5-nitro acid as the dipotassium salt: each salt can then

be purified. Moreover, it is possible to ascertain, approximately, how much of each acid is produced during nitration.

The older methods of separation by crystallisation of the acids or of their barium salts yield the 5-nitro acid in the pure state, whilst the 3-nitro acid is not obtained pure. Generally it can be said that the recorded work on 3-nitrosalicylic acid and its derivatives is unreliable; this can be seen from the following tables, the first of which gives the melting points of the acids.

<i>Melting points.</i>		
	Previous workers. Meldrum and Hirve.	
3-Nitro-salicylic acid (hydrated).	125°	128-129°
.. (anhydrous).	145°	148-149°
5-Nitro-salicylic acid.	228°	228°

The Methyl Esters.

Knowledge of the methyl esters of 3-nitro- and 5-nitro-salicylic acids was uncertain and confused: in Beilstein's *Handbuch der Organischen Chemie*, 1896, 2, 1509), they are described as ethyl esters. Smith and Knerr (*Am. Chem. J.*, 1886, 8, 49), by passing nitrogen trioxide into a solution in ether of methyl salicylate, obtained two substances neither of which is correctly named by these authors. Keller (*Arch. Pharm.*, 1908, 246, 1) by various methods obtained from 3-nitrosalicylic acid (m. p. 144°) three methyl derivatives for one of which he could not account. We prepared each ester from methyl alcohol and the respective acid. The following table gives the observed melting points.

	Smith and Knerr.	Keller.	Meldrum and Hirve.
Methyl 3-nitro-salicylate	118°	93°	132°
Methyl 5-nitrosalicylate	96°	...	119°

By following Smith and Knerr's method we obtained a mixture from which we separated three substances, m. p. 132°, 118°, and 96° respectively. Of these the first is methyl 3-nitrosalicylate and the second (named in error by Smith and Knerr) is methyl 5-nitrosalicylate. The third, m. p. 96°, we found to be a eutectic mixture: when hydrolysed by potassium hydroxide it was possible to separate

the characteristic potassium-salts of 3-nitro- and 5-nitrosalicylic acids. Keller's substance, m. p. 93°, can be accounted for as being nearly the same as the eutectic mixture, and as having been obtained from a specimen of the 3-nitro acid that was contaminated with the 5-nitro acid.

The Ethyl Esters.*

Ethyl 3-nitrosalicylate was prepared by Hübner (*Annalen*, 1879, 195, 34) from the silver salt and ethyl iodide and by Zacharios (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1871, (ii) 43, 434) from alcohol and the acid in presence of sulphuric acid.

Ethyl 5-nitrosalicylate was prepared by Hübner (*loc. cit.*) from the silver salt and ethyl iodide. Thieme (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1891, (ii), 43, 469) and Herre (*Ber.*, 1895, 28, 498) prepared it from alcohol and the acid in presence of sulphuric acid. We prepared these substances from alcohol and the respective acids. The following table gives the observed melting points:—

	Hubner.	Zacharios.	Herre.	Thieme.	Meldrum and Hirve.
Ethyl 3-nitrosalicylate	...	44.5°	46.5°
Ethyl 5-nitrosalicylate	93°	...	96°	96°	102°

The Amides.

Hübner (*Annalen*, 1879, 198, 35) prepared the amides by heating together the respective ethyl esters and alcoholic ammonia. We prepared them by shaking a mixture of the respective ethyl esters, alcohol and ammonia solution. From the resulting mixture of the amide and the ammonium salt we precipitated the amide by means of potassium hydroxide solution in the case of the 3-nitro-acid: the potassium salt of the acid is precipitated first and then that of the amide; in the case of the 5-nitro acid the potassium salt of the amide is first precipitated.

* Hirsch (*Ber.*, 1900, 33, 3289) reported a method by which he obtained (a) 3-nitrosalicylic acid, m. p. 144°, and its ethyl ester, m. p. 118°; (b) 5-nitrosalicylic acid, m. p. 230°, and its ethyl ester, m. p. 93°. There is no proof that the substances, m. p. 118° and m. p. 93°, were ethyl esters or pure substances. No analyses are given.

	Hubner.	Meldrum and Hirve.
3-Nitrosalicylamide	... 145-146°	155°
5-Nitrosalicylamide	... 225°	225°

EXPERIMENTAL.

Numerous experiments have led to the following details for the preparation and the separation of 3-nitro- and 5-nitro-salicylic acids.

Nitration.—Salicylic acid (100 g.) was mixed with nitric acid (*d* 1.2 ; 200 c. c.). The mixture was well shaken from time to time and kept cool. After twenty-four hours it was shaken automatically for two hours. The solid product was then collected by filtration and washed with water.

Separation.—The solid was dissolved in a hot concentrated solution of potassium carbonate so that the solution, being neutral to litmus, contained the mono-potassium salts. The less soluble salt (of the 3-nitro-acid) separated as pale yellow needles. A further yield was obtained by concentrating the filtrate. The mother-liquor was rendered alkaline by strong potassium hydroxide. The composition of the salts at this stage is $C_6H_4(NO_2).COOK.OK$: this salt of the 5-nitro acid separated as yellow needles. The mother-liquor was neutralised by acetic acid and a further yield of the potassium salt of the 3-nitro acid was obtained. The final mother-liquor contained the potassium salts of the nitro acids, unchanged salicylic acid and *o*-nitrophenol in small amounts.

The salts were recrystallised from water. The respective acids were liberated on addition of dilute sulphuric acid to the aqueous solution of pure salts and were finally recrystallised from water.

We also studied the methods for nitration laid down by previous workers using our own method of separating the nitro acids. In each experiment 100 g. of salicylic acid were used. The results are shown in the following table:—

Nitration of Salicylic Acid.

Authors.	Nitrating agent.	Temperature.	3-Nitro acid.	Yield 5-Nitro acid.	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenol.
Meldrum and Hirve.	HNO_3 , (<i>d</i> 1.2) 200 c. c.	Room temperature.	33.5 g.	55 g.	Little.
Meldola, Foster and Brightman.	One part HNO_3 and four parts water.	100° for one hour.	22.5 g.	50 g.	Much.
Deninger (for 3-nitro-).	$NaNO_3$ and H_2SO_4 , (<i>d</i> 1.52)	Free rise of temperature.	15 g.	22.5 g.	Much.
Deninger (for 5-nitro).	$NaNO_3$ and H_2EO_4 , (<i>d</i> 1.52)	Below 15°, finally warming to 50°.	15 g.	20 g.	Little.

3-Nitrosalicylic acid forms long yellowish-white needles, $C_7H_5O_3N$, H_2O , m. p. 128-129°. The anhydrous acid is yellow, m. p. 148-149°. (Found: H_2O , 8.95. $C_7H_5O_3N$, H_2O requires H_2O , 8.96 per cent.).

Potassium Salt.—(Found: K, 17.65. $C_7H_5O_3NK$ requires K, 17.65 per cent.).

The phenolic potassium salt was prepared by adding excess of strong potassium hydroxide solution to the acid. Red coloured microscopic needles separated from the solution, which were collected and washed with a little alcohol. On standing the substance absorbs moisture turning yellow, and changes again to red on heating. (Found: K, 30.63. $C_7H_5O_3NK_2$ requires K, 30.11 per cent.).

Barium Salts.—In accordance with previous work our analysis showed that the composition of the neutral barium salt is $(C_7H_5O_3N)_2Ba$ (the solubility at 31° is 0.15): that of the phenolic barium salt is $C_7H_5O_3NBa$, $1\frac{1}{2} H_2O$.

5-Nitrosalicylic acid crystallises in long white needles, m. p. 228°. It is difficultly soluble in water and easily soluble in acetic acid, alcohol and ether.

Potassium 5-nitrosalicylate was prepared by adding the acid to strong potassium carbonate solution till it was neutral to litmus. The properties are given above. (Found: K, 17.32. $C_7H_5O_3NK$ required K, 17.65 per cent.).

The phenolic potassium salt was obtained by adding strong potassium hydroxide solution to the above neutral salt or to the acid itself. It crystallises as yellow needles. (Found: H_2O , 11.85; K, 26.52. $C_7H_5O_3NK_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ requires H_2O , 12.20; K, 26.44 per cent.).

Barium Salts.—In accordance with previous work, our analyses showed that the composition of the neutral barium salt is $(C_7H_5O_3N)_2Ba$, $4H_2O$ (the solubility at 31° is 1.33): that of the phenolic barium salt is $C_7H_5O_3NBa \cdot H_2O$.

Methyl 3-Nitrosalicylate.—Pure dehydrated 3-nitrosalicylic acid (15 g.) was dissolved in methyl alcohol (60 c.c.) and dry hydrochloric acid gas (6 g.) was passed into it. The mixture was refluxed on the water-bath for four hours. On cooling crystals separated which were collected; a further yield was obtained from the mother-liquor on evaporation.

It is slightly soluble in methyl and ethyl alcohols, cold ether, cold chloroform, and benzene.

It crystallised from ethyl alcohol in beautiful octahedra of a pale yellow colour, m.p. 132°; yield 15 g. (Found: N, 7.11. $C_8H_7O_5N$ requires N, 7.10 per cent.)

Methyl 5-nitrosalicylate was prepared in a similar way. The excess of alcohol was removed by distillation. It recrystallised from ethyl alcohol in long white needles, m.p. 119°.

It is easily soluble in ether, cold chloroform and benzene and less easily soluble in ethyl and methyl alcohols. (Found: N, 7.39. $C_8H_7O_5N$ requires N, 7.10 per cent.)

With a view to account for the substance, m.p. 96°, obtained by Smith and Knerr (*loc. cit.*), we prepared it by their method obtaining at the same time substances identical with our methyl esters. The substance was hydrolysed by potassium hydroxide, and from the hydrolysed mixture 3-nitro- and 5-nitro-salicylic acids were obtained separately by the method adopted for the separation in this paper. The substance, m.p. 96° (1.2 g.), gave the 3-nitro acid (0.25 g.) and the 5-nitro acid (0.7 g.).

Ethyl 3-Nitrosalicylate.—Pure anhydrous 3-nitrosalicylic acid (18 g.) was dissolved in absolute alcohol (72 c.c.) and dry hydrochloric acid gas (8 g.) was passed into it, and the mixture was refluxed on the water-bath for 6 hours. On cooling an oily layer separated, which crystallised slowly; the mother-liquor on evaporation gave a further yield: total 16.5 g.

Ethyl 3-nitrosalicylate is readily soluble in methyl and ethyl alcohols, acetic acid, chloroform and slightly soluble in cold petroleum ether and benzene. From petroleum ether it separates in well defined cubes, m.p. 48.5°. (Found: N, 6.67. $C_8H_7O_5N$ requires N, 6.63 per cent.)

Ethyl 5-Nitrosalicylate.—Pure 5-nitrosalicylic acid (30 g.) was dissolved in absolute alcohol (120 c.c.) and dry hydrochloric acid gas (11 g.) was passed into it, and the mixture was refluxed on the water-bath for about 5 hours: on cooling, the ester separated in long slender needles. The mother-liquor, on evaporation, gave a further yield: total 27 g.

Ethyl 5-nitrosalicylate is easily soluble in hot acetic acid and alcohol and difficultly soluble in cold acetic acid, alcohol, ether and benzene: easily soluble in chloroform. It can be best crystallised from acetic acid or alcohol, from which it is obtained as long slender

needles, m.p. 102°. (Found: N, 6.66. $C_9H_9O_3N$ requires N, 6.63 per cent.).

3-Nitrosalicylamide.—Ethyl 3-nitrosalicylate (10 g.) was dissolved in absolute alcohol (100 c.c.) in a glass stoppered bottle, and cooled. Strong ammonia solution (200 c.c.) was added to it, when the ester was precipitated. This mixture was automatically shaken until a clear solution was obtained. After driving away the excess of ammonia by heating on the water-bath, the solution was acidified, and the resulting precipitate was neutralised by potassium hydroxide solution, when potassium 3-nitrosalicylate was precipitated. On adding strong potassium hydroxide solution to the mother-liquor, the potassium salt of the amide was precipitated. It was collected, washed, dissolved in water again, and the amide liberated by acidifying. The pure substance was obtained on recrystallising it from water in pale yellow needles, m.p. 155°.

3-Nitrosalicylamide is very soluble in acetic acid and nitrobenzene, easily soluble in ethyl alcohol and hot water, difficultly soluble in chloroform and benzene and insoluble in petroleum ether. (Found: N, 15.52. $C_7H_6O_4N_2$ requires N, 15.39 per cent.).

The *potassium salt* was recrystallised from water: small orange coloured needles. (Found: K, 16.43. $C_7H_6O_4N_2K, H_2O$ requires K, 16.39 per cent.).

5-Nitrosalicylamide.—Ethyl 5-nitrosalicylate (20 g.) was dissolved in absolute alcohol (100 c.c.) and then strong ammonia solution (30 c.c.) was added, when the ester was precipitated. The amide was prepared and purified as in the preceding case.

It was crystallised from methyl alcohol: needles and rectangular plates, m.p. 225°.

5-Nitrosalicylamide is extremely soluble in nitrobenzene, easily soluble in acetic acid, moderately soluble in methyl and ethyl alcohol, difficultly soluble in petroleum, ether and benzene and insoluble in chloroform. (Found: N, 15.50. $C_7H_6O_4N$ requires N, 15.39 per cent.).

The *potassium salt* ($C_6H_5.NO_2.OK.CONH_2.H_2O$) crystallised from water in cluster of yellow silky needles: (Found: H_2O , 7.52; K, 16.43. $C_7H_6O_4NK, H_2O$ requires H_2O , 7.56; K, 16.39 per cent.).

